

Research Article

Socio-Economic Profile of Women Entrepreneurs in Krishna District, Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract

The paper attempts to analyze the Socio Economic profile of Women Entrepreneurs. The Entrepreneurship is very important criteria for economic development. The role of women entrepreneurs can't be denied in this process. Women in this world as well as in our nation face many hardships but the increased span of education and awareness helped to an own mark for them in this entrepreneurs.

Keywords: Enterprise, market creation, entrepreneurial contribution, socio economic development, employment, Women Entrepreneurs

Introduction

"An enterprise owned and controlled by a woman and having a minimum financial interest of 51 percent of the capital and giving at least 51 percent of the employment generated in the enterprise to women" is the definition of a women entrepreneur. The term "entrepreneur" comes from the French word "entreprenre," which refers to someone who took on the risk of starting a new business. applied to those who were engaged in hasty military action in the early 16th century. Entrepreneur was a term used in the 17th century to describe civil engineering tasks like building and fortification. For the first time it was used in commerce in 18th century to refer to a trader who buys and sells products at varying price rates.

Entrepreneurs are essential to the development of the economy. They have been referred to as the human agents required to raise finance for exploration, resource discovery, market creation, and commerce. It will be argued that whether a nation experiences wealth or poverty depends on the entrepreneurial contribution.

Statement of the Problem

The second biggest group of prospective entrepreneurs in India is made up of women, who make up half of the country's overall population. The nation's economic and social growth is significantly influenced by women. Entrepreneurship development is an economic process in which the entrepreneur acts as the significant factor in the said process. It will be very productive to analyse the process of transformation of social structure and the instrumentality in the emergence of the women entrepreneurs from the female gender.

The state of Andhra Pradesh had made a significant stride in the areas of socio-economic development and these projects into the higher levels of literacy among the women gender. The increased span of education process and the increased levels of awareness among the Indian women towards the economic activities in the societies had paved the way for them to have

their own mark on the business roads which were monopolistically occupied by men in the society. These factors had played a significant role in the social and economic transformation process of women into successful entrepreneurs. The existing business environment in the society had distinctively acted as the motivating factor for the increased level of women entrepreneurial activities in the state of Andhra Pradesh.

The micro enterprises play a significant role in the industrial scenario across the state of Andhra Pradesh. The micro enterprises generally involve local labour with easy availability and feasibility and thus this industrial sector acts as the main provider of employment to large section of people in the society through direct or indirect means. The present study involves some of the aspects of socio-economic profile of women micro entrepreneurs in Krishna district of Andhra Pradesh.

Review of Literature

Vijayakumar (2020), study observed that women act as the significant gender in the total population of the nation and they comprise innate qualities and greater capacities to act as the significant contributor for the overall economic development of the country. In order to enrich the women entrepreneurs, special policies and programs are to be framed and should be strategically implemented in order to support their entrepreneurial activities and a sense of culture among them.

In order to create awareness among the women towards the entrepreneurial culture and economic development, the media plays the prime role and it acts as the suitable platform to mould the enthusiastic women towards entrepreneurial activities. In order to explore the various dimensions of business avenues, the advanced countries are in the urgent need of motivating and encouraging women entrepreneurial activities because the availability of human resources (work force) in terms of women's gender is very plentiful and promptly available. Universally, the business world has recognized the importance of women entrepreneurship in the economic development of the society and in future the women entrepreneurship will act as the effective strategy for handling and to overcome all types of business challenges.

Ramesh.B (2021), study observed that women constitute 50 percent of the total population across the nation and they play a significant role in the economic development of the nation. Basically, Indian society is said to be male dominated and the female gender were assumed to be socially and economically dependent on the male members in their families. In general, women entrepreneurs will come across various social and economic hurdles or bottlenecks like social and cultural barriers, lack of education, lack of financial support, lack of self confidence and limited managerial and administrative capabilities. There are various pull and push factors that influence the participation and development of women entrepreneurship. The nation has to formulate various entrepreneurial policies towards the development of women entrepreneurs and these steps were already initiated through the 7th, 8th and 9th five year plans successively. With the emerging technological innovations in the economic and industrial sector, women entrepreneurs are emerging as the potential economic and work force and this was duly recognized by the policy makers of the nation and steps are being taken in order to promote the women entrepreneurs in the society.

Objectives and Methods

The main objective of the paper is to analyse the socio-economic profile of women entrepreneurs in Krishna district of Andhra Pradesh. The size of the sample is 306 women entrepreneurs. The sample is taken from four revenue divisions of Krishna district in Andhra Pradesh. The selection of sample is made by using simple random sampling technique.

Marital status of the sample women entrepreneurs

The marital status of the women who own microbusinesses makes incentives and recognition necessary. In the current research, it is one of the social factors. The need and commitment of married people are often stronger than those of single people. Similar to how varied obligations in life depend on statuses like divorce and widowhood. The respondents of the current research are divided into four marital status categories: single, married, separated, and widowed. Table-1 displays the respondents' marital statuses.

Table:1 Marital status of the sample women entrepreneurs

S. No	Marital status	Frequency	Percent
1	Unmarried	9	(2.94)
2	Married	279	(91.18)
3	Separated	13	(4.25)
4	Widowed	5	(1.63)
5	Total	306	(100.00)

Source: Primary data

Table-1 explains about the distribution of sample women entrepreneurs by their marital status. Out of the total sample highest group (91.18 percent) were married and only 2.94 per cent were unmarried, 4.25 per cent women entrepreneurs are separated from their family and 1.63 per cent are widowed. This shows that majority of the women entrepreneurs were married, 91 per cent of the women entrepreneurs started their enterprises after their marriage to aid his family and to share the family burden with their husbands.

Age-wise distribution of the sample women entrepreneurs

Age is the most crucial social feature among female micro entrepreneurs because it affects respondents' exposure, curiosity, willingness to take risks, and adaptability. Younger people are more willing to take risks than older people, while older people have more experience. For the responders to improve their entrepreneurial behaviour, both these qualities of experience and risk orientation are crucial. The age ranges for the respondents in this survey are as follows: under 25, between 25 and 35, between 36 and 45, between 46 and 55, and above 55.

Table-2 analyses the distribution of sample entrepreneurs by their age groups in the above table. Out of the total sample 48.04 percent are 30-39 years, 24.18 percent are between 40-49 years, 11.76 percent are between 20-29 years, 9.48 per cent are between 50-59 years and very few 5.56 percent are below 20 years age group. This shows that majority of the women entrepreneurs are in the 30-39 age.

Table:2 Age-wise distribution of the sample women entrepreneurs

S. No	Age group(in years)	Frequency	Percent
1	Below 20	17	(5.56)
2	20 - 29	36	(11.76)
3	30 - 39	147	(48.04)
4	40 - 49	74	(24.18)
5	50 - 59	29	(9.48)
6	60 & above	3	(0.98)
	Total	306	(100.00)

Source: Primary data

Social Category of Sample Respondents

In India's traditional varna system, caste is a sub-division. All people, including women, used to have their occupations determined by their caste in the past. A person's attitude and mentality toward business are shaped by their caste. Caste continues to be the foundation of member action even when education level affects an individual's behaviour. The distribution of sample women entrepreneurs by social category is presented in the table-3. The data shows that majority of sample respondents belong to Backward Caste (52.63%), followed by 35.29 per cent are Forward Category and 11.11 per cent are Schedule Caste and 1.96 per cent are Scheduled tribes. This indicates that majority of the women entrepreneurs are from the Backward Class.

Table:3 Distribution of the Sample Women Entrepreneurs by Social Category

S. No.	Caste	Frequency	Percent
1	Open Category	108	(35.29)
2	Backward Caste	158	(51.63)
3	Schedule Caste	34	(11.11)
4	Scheduled Tribes	6	(1.96)
	Total	306	(100.00)

Source: Primary data

Education

The respondents' formal education is reflected in their level of education. The current research takes into account the respondents' education degree as one of the key determinants of their comprehension, tolerance, scientific orientation, risk orientation, and innovativeness. Illiterate, S.S.L.C., upper secondary school level, undergraduate, and others, which include diploma and polytechnic education, are the different categories for educational attainment. The table-4 gives on the distribution of sample women entrepreneurs by education levels. It is evident that 57.19 per cent studied up to Intermediate, followed by 21.90 per cent with SSC, 13.07 per cent with Graduates, 4.25 per cent are Post Graduates and the remaining 3.59 per cent are having below SSC level. This indicated that majority of the women entrepreneurs are Intermediate education. There are no illiterates among the sample respondents in the study area.

Table:4 Educational qualifications of the sample women entrepreneurs

S. No	Qualification	Frequency	Percent
1	Below SSC	11	(3.59)
2	SSC	67	(21.90)
3	Intermediate	175	(57.19)
4	Graduate	40	(13.07)
5	Post graduate	13	4.25)
	Total	306	(100.00)

Source: Primary data

Income status of the sample women entrepreneurs

The annual family income of the sample women entrepreneurs in the study area is given in table-5. It shows that 40.85 percent of the respondents are having the annual family income in the range below Rs. 2,00,000 to Rs.4,00,000, 27.78 per cent of the respondents were having the annual family income in the range of Rs.4.0 lakhs to 6.0 lakhs, 9.80 per cent of the respondents

are having the annual family income in the above Rs.6 lakhs, 2.61 per cent of the respondents are having the annual family income in the below one lakh rupees.

The result shows that a major proportion of the women entrepreneurs in the study area are having the annual family income in the range of Rs.2,00,000 to 4,00,000. It is inferred from the study that major proportion of women entrepreneurs in the study area are having sizable income levels and the entrepreneurial activities can rise the income levels of the women entrepreneur families the entrepreneurial activities will economically empower the women and raises their standard of living in the society.

Table:5 Income status of the sample women entrepreneurs

S. No	Income levels (Rs. in lakhs)	Frequency	Percent
1	< 0.5	3	(0.98)
2	0.5 – 1.0	5	(1.63)
3	1.0 – 2.0	58	(18.95)
4	2.0 – 4.0	125	(40.85)
5	4.0 – 6.0	85	(27.78)
6	> 6.0	30	(9.80)
	Total	306	(100.00)

Source: Primary data

Conclusion

Women constitute half of the population in the world as well as in India. The socio-economic conditions play an important role among the women micro entrepreneurs. Income levels, education, marital status and social conditions influence the women entrepreneurs to a great extent. In order to increase the participation of women in enterprises, the government has to take initiative to provide training and credit facilities to the women entrepreneurs.

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Citation: A.Madhavi 2024. Socio-Economic Profile of Women Entrepreneurs in Krishna District, Andhra Pradesh. *International Journal of Academic Research*, 11(3): 8-12.

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